

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SOYBEAN IN AMRAVATI DISTRICT

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Abstract

In this study, an attempt has been made to study Yield gap analysis of soybean in Amravati district with view to workout cost and returns of soybean production, to estimate technical, allocative and economic efficiency in soybean production. The present study was conducted in Vidarbha region's Amravati district. The district was chosen on purpose. Three tehsils were chosen for this study, and four villages were chosen random from each tehsil. Ten farmers are chosen from each village. Primary data for the agricultural year 2022-2023 were acquired through the survey method from respondent farmers utilizing pre-tested interviews and a well-structured schedule.

The cost per hectare of soybean crop was highest in the small size group i.e. Rs. 70078.67 followed by medium size group (Rs.66339.62) and large size group (Rs. 50741.34) respectively and overall level it was Rs.63783.87. The output-input ratio for overall size group at Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, Cost C₃ were 1.94, 1.94, 1.85, 1.33, 1.73, 1.26, 1.14 respectively.

The mean level of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency has been estimated as 95.26 per cent, 62.72 per cent, and 65.92 per cent in soybean cultivation. The results indicate the potential for improving allocative efficiency further by utilizing inputs more efficiently.

Keywords: Soybean, Cost of cultivation, Efficiency, output-input ratio.

Introduction:

Soybean, scientifically known as *Glycine max* (L.) Merrill, holds the title of being the most economically significant bean worldwide. Belonging to the legume family, soybean originates from East Asia and stands as the paramount legume and oilseed crop globally. Soybean is mainly cultivated as a rainfed crop in India, primarily across the states of Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Rajasthan, on vertisols and associated soils. The significant fluctuations in rainfall, both temporally and spatially, pose a significant challenge to its successful cultivation. Its remarkable adaptability extends across various soils and climates, rendering it a versatile agricultural asset. Furthermore, soybean serves as a crucial source of cost-effective, high-quality protein and oil. With a protein content of 40%, surpassing that of all other food crops, and an oil content of 18%, trailing only groundnut among food legumes, soybean commands a substantial presence in the global oilseed market, accounting for an estimated 50% of output. Soybean oil, the world's second most significant vegetable oil following palm oil, contributes to approximately 25% of global consumption of vegetable and animal oils and fats.

Between 2011 and 2021-22, the overall soybean cultivation area in India increased from 10.11 million hectares to 12.27 million hectares, accompanied by a rise in production from 12.21 million metric tons (MMT) to 12.99 MMT. This expansion in cultivation area signifies a growth trend compared to the base year.

Soybean was first introduced to Maharashtra in the mid-1990s (1984-85). Its popularity surged due to its short growing cycle (90-115 days) and superior yields compared to other oilseeds, whether grown under rainfed or irrigated conditions. In the 2021-22 season, Maharashtra witnessed soybean cultivation over an area of 46.91 lakh hectares, yielding a production of 45.446 lakh metric tons and achieving a productivity of 1125 kg per hectare.

In the Amravati Division, the soybean cultivation area measured 2.418 lakh hectares in 2022-23, with a corresponding production of 1205 lakh hectares and a productivity rate of 2.914 kg per hectare.

Materials And Method:**1. Cost concepts**

The cost concepts were used to estimate the cost of cultivation. The cost concepts i.e. Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, Cost

C₃ which are generally followed in farm management studies were adopted for the present study and examined as below.

COST "A₁"

It is the actual paid out cost incurred by the cultivator. This cost comprise of the expenditure incurred by the farmers in cash was well kind for the cultivator of soybean in respect of following items.

1. Value of hired human labour
2. Value of bullock labour
3. Value of machine labour
4. Value of seeds
5. Value of manure
6. Value of fertilizer used
7. Value of irrigation
8. Value of plant protection measures adopted
9. Depreciation charge
10. Land revenue and other taxes
11. Miscellaneous charges
12. Repairing charges
13. Incidental charges
14. Interest on working capital @ 6 per cent annum

COST "A₂"

Cost A₁ + Rent paid for leased-in land

COST "B₁"

Cost A₁ + Interest value of owned fixed capital assets (excluding land)

COST "B₂"

Cost B₁ + Rental value of owned land (net of land revenue) and rent paid for leased-in land

COST "C₁"

Cost B₁ + Imputed value of family labour

COST "C₂"

Cost B₂ + Imputed value of family labour

COST "C₃"

Cost C₂ + 10% of Cost C₂

Gross And Net Return

Gross Return : Return obtained from the sale of crop output
i.e. main products and by products

Net Return: Net return was computed at different standard cost concepts i.e. Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, Cost C₃ by deducting respective cost from the gross returns.

Input-output ratio

profitability of crop production cannot be justified completely unless input-output ratios are worked out. This is the ratio which represents returns obtained per rupee of investment. It worked out by dividing returns by the respective cost.

The input-output ratio was worked out on the basis of standard cost concepts.

a. Input – output ratio at Cost A₁

Input – Output Ratio

b. Input – Output Ratio at Cost A₂

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost A}_2} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost A}_1}$$

c. Input – Output Ratio at Cost B₁

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost B}_1}$$

d. Input – Output Ratio at Cost B₂

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost B}_2}$$

e. Input – Output Ratio at Cost C₁

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost C}_1}$$

f. Input – Output Ratio at Cost C₂

Input – Output Ratio

g. Input – Output Ratio at Cost C₃

$$\text{Input – Output Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost C}_2} = \frac{\text{Gross Income}}{\text{Cost C}_2}$$

Technical and Allocative Efficiency

In the present study stochastic production frontier function and stochastic frontier profit functions were used to determine the farm-specific technical and economic efficiencies respectively.

Stochastic production frontier function -

In the present study, the stochastic frontier approach was used to measure the farm specific efficiencies of kharif soybean crop. (Aigner et al., 1977; Kalirajan and Shand, 1889; Sharma and Datta, 1997) The stochastic frontier model is called a ‘composed’ model because the error term is composed of two independent elements, namely -

$$\Sigma_i = v_i - u_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

The term v_i is the symmetric component and permits random variation in output due to factors like weather and plant disease. It is assumed to be identically and independently distributed $v_i \approx N(0, \sigma^2 v)$. A one-sided component ($u_i \geq 0$) reflects technical efficiency relative to stochastic frontier $Q_i = Q(Xk_i, \beta) e^{v_i}$. Thus $u_i = 0$ for any farm lying on the frontier while $u_i > 0$ for any farm lying below the frontier. Hence expression (u_i)

represents the amount by which the frontier exceeds realized output. The distribution of u_i is assumed to be half-normal.

A measure of technical efficiency was first introduced by Farrell (1957) for a cross-section of firms by using a deterministic approach. He illustrated his ideas of efficiency using a simple example involving firms that use two inputs (x_1 and x_2) to produce a single output (q), under the assumption of constant returns to scale. The curve SS' in following figure represents the unit isoquant of fully efficient firms and permits the measurement of technical efficiency. If a given firm uses quantities of inputs, defined by the point P, to produce a unit of output, the technical inefficiency of that firm is represented by the distance QP, which is the amount in which all inputs could be proportionately reduced without a reduction in output. This is usually expressed in percentage terms by the ratio QP/OP , which represented the percentage in which all inputs can be optimally reduced to achieve technically efficient production. Hence, the technical efficiency (TE) of a firm can be measured by the ratio

$$TE = OQ/OP$$

Technical inefficiency is equal to $1 - OQ/OP$ and takes a value between zero and one. Hence, it provides an indicator of the degree of technical inefficiency of the firm. A value of one implies that the firm is fully technically efficient.

Specification of the model

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + (V_i - U_i)$$

Where,

Y_i = Output of Specific crop (Soybean) (Quintals/ha)

X_1 = Human labour (days/ha)

X_2 = Machine hours (hrs/ha)

X_3 = Quantity of seeds (kg/ha)

X_4 = Quantity of fertilizers (kg/ha)

V_i = Random variable

U_i = Farm specific technical efficiency related variable

β_0 = Intercept/Constant

Stochastic profit frontier function

Stochastic frontier profit function was used to estimate economic efficiency of Soybean crop. (Ali and Flinn, 1989; Rahman, 2003; Galawat and Yabe, 2012). The stochastic profit frontier function was estimated as-

$$\Pi_i = f(X_i, P_i) + (v_i - u_i)$$

where,

Π_i = Normalized profit at cost-A of the i^{th} farmer.

X_i = The vector of variable input prices divided by output price faced by the i^{th} farm.

P_i = The vector of fixed factor of the i^{th} farm.

V_i = random error due to factors outside the control of the farmers.

U_i = A non- negative random variable associated with economic inefficiency component

The economic efficiency in relation to the stochastic profit frontier is given by,

$$EE_i = \exp(-u_i)$$

Specification of the model

$$\ln \Pi_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + (V_i - U_i)$$

Where,

Π_i = Normalized profit at Cost-A of the i^{th} farmer.

X_1 = Human labour wage rate per normalized by output price of i^{th} farmer.

X_2 = Machine wage rate per hour normalized by output price of i^{th} farmer.

X_3 = Price of Seed per kg normalized by the i^{th} farmer.

X_4 = Quantity of fertilizer per kg normalized by output price of i^{th} farmer.

V_i = Random variable

U_i = Farm-specific economic efficiency related variable

β_0 = Intercept

Factor price is obtained by dividing the price of input with the output price. Allocative efficiency was estimated by dividing economic efficiency with technical efficiency for each farm.

$$AE_i = EE_i/TE_i$$

Result and Discussion:

1. Economics of Soybean production

The share of each them in the total cost provides necessary due to economizing costs. The cost has been determined on the basis of standard cost concept i.e. Cost "A₁", Cost "A₂", Cost "B₁", Cost "B₂", Cost "C₁", Cost "C₂", Cost "C₃". The different cost concepts have different utilities in research. Here an attempt has been made to estimate the figures of cost of soybean crop in the study area and presented in succeeding tables.

Table 1.1.1 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for small farmer

							(Rs/ha)
Sr.No	Item	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost/Unit ofinput	Total Cost perha	% to cost C ₃
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	19.63	298	6543.26	9.33
		Female	Days	17.93	197	3984.40	5.68
		Total				10527.67	15.02
2	Bullock Labour	Hired		5.98	589	3586.2	5.11
		Owned		1.00	439	498.1	0.71
		Total				4084.29	5.82
3	Machine Charges	Hired	Hours	3.97	430	2775	3.95
		Owned	Hours	0.46	364	275.86	0.39
		Total				3051.72	4.35
4	Seed		Kg	74.1	122.22	8153.2	11.63
5	Manures		Tonne	12.41	160	1985.60	2.83
6	Fertilizers	N	Kg	46.9	13.04	612.0	0.87
		P	Kg	50.0	45.25	2262.1	3.22
		K	Kg	10.0	20	199.6	0.28
		Total				3073.7	4.38
8	Irrigation Charges	Rs				716.48	1.02
9	Plant Protection		Litre			3000.80	4.28
10	Incidental Charges	Rs				579.12	0.82
11	Repairing Charges	Rs				500.13	0.71
12	Working Capital					40101.20	57.22
13	Int. on working Capital @ 6%					1203.03	1.71
14	Depreciation	Rs				941.22	1.34
15	Land Revenue	Rs				208.49	0.29
16	Cost A₁					42453.95	60.70
17	Rental value of leased land					0.00	0.00
18	Cost A₂					42453.95	60.70
19	Fixed capital					8949.62	12.77
20	Int. on Fixed Capital @ 10%					894.96	1.27
21	Cost B₁					43348.91	61.85
22	Rental value of land	Rs				15516.35	22.14
23	Cost B₂					58809.42	83.91
24	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	12.05	298	3614.94	5.51
		Female	Days	6.42	197	1283.52	1.83
		Total				4898.47	6.98
25	Cost C₁					48247.38	68.84
26	Cost C₂					63707.89	90.90

1.1 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for small farmers

The per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean for small farmers was workout and presented in Table 1.1.1

It is revealed that from the table 1 that, the per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean at cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" was Rs. 42453.95, cost "B₁" was Rs. 43348.91 whereas cost "B₂" was Rs. 58809.42 and cost "C₁" was Rs. 48247.38 Cost "C₂" was Rs.63707.89 whereas cost "C₃" was Rs.70078.67 The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" (60.70 per cent). In cost "A₁" share of Seed was 11.6 per cent, hired human labour 15.02 per cent, Fertilizer 4.38 per cent, machine hours 4.35 per cent, bullock labour 5.82 per cent, Plant Protection 4.28 per cent. all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket.

Cost 'B₁' contributes to 61.85 per cent, Cost B₂ contribute 83.91 per cent. The share of family labour was 6.98 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by small farmers was 19.37 quintal with gross return of Rs. 94013.98 In case of small size group the per quintal cost of production was Rs 3617.18

27	Cost C ₃					70078.67	100.00
28	Main Produce		Qtls	19.37	4782.2	92961.60	132.65
29	By produce		Qtls	8.78	254	1383.52	1.97
30	Gross Value		Rs			94013.98	134.15
31	Per Qtl. Cost of Production					3617.18	5.16

1.2 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for Medium farmers

The per hectare cost of cultivation of Soybean for Medium farmers was workout and presented in Tables 1.2.1

Table 1.2.1 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for Medium farmers

(Rs/ha)

Sr.No	Item	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost/Unit of input	Total Cost per ha	% to cost C ₃
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	13.96	303	4187.70	6.39
		Female	Days	12.54	196	2507.89	3.82
		Total				6695.58	10.21
2	Bullock Labour	Hired		2.43	578	1457.41	2.22
		Owned		0.49	446	244.48	0.37
		Total				1701.89	2.59
3	Machine Charges	Hired	Hours	2.48	694	1735.65	2.65
		Owned	Hours	0.57	557	340.69	0.52
		Total				2076.34	3.17
4	Seed		Kg	72.96	110	8025.23	12.24
5	Manures		Qtls	5.71	167	913.44	1.39
6	Fertilizers	N	Kg	46.21	13.04	602.52	0.92
		P	Kg	49.22	45.25	2227.3	3.40
		K	Kg	9.82	20	196.5	0.30
		Total				3026.3	4.61
8	Irrigation Charges		Rs			323.8	0.49
9	Incidental Charges					417.7	0.64
10	Plant Protection Charges		Rs			2510.3	3.83
11	Repairing Charges		Rs			422.16	0.64
12	Working Capital					33377.9	50.89
13	Int. on working Capital @ 6 %					1015.80	1.56
14	Depreciation		Rs			1784.4	2.72
15	Land Revenue		Rs			33860.1	51.63
16	Cost A₁					36881.57	56.54
17	Rental value of leased land					0.00	0.00
18	Cost A₂					36881.57	56.54
19	Fixed capital					23347.9	35.60
20	Int. on Fixed Capital @10%					2334.8	3.53
21	Cost B₁					39216.37	60.13
22	Rental value of land		Rs			17974.05	27.41
23	Cost B₂					57190.42	87.69
24	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	4.75	303	1424.29	2.17
		Female	Days	3.39	196	678.23	1.03
		Total				2102.52	3.21
25	Cost C₁					41318.89	63.35
26	Cost C₂					59292.95	90.91
27	Cost C₃					65222.24	100.00
28	Main Produce		Qtls	22.07	4843.59	105937.92	162.43
29	By produce		Qtls	11.89	243	2304.41	3.53
30	Gross Value		Rs			108242.34	165.96
31	Per Qtl Cost of Production					2955.24	4.53

It is revealed that from the table 1.2.1 that, the per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean at cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" was Rs.36881.57, cost "B₁" was Rs.39216.37 whereas cost "B₂" was Rs. 57190.42 and cost

"C₁" was Rs. 41318.89 Cost "C₂" was Rs.59292.95 whereas cost "C₃" was Rs.65222.24. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" (56.54 per cent). In cost "A₁" share of Seed was

12.24 per cent, hired human labour 10.21 per cent, Fertilizer 4.61 per cent, machine hours 3.17 per cent, bullock labour 2.59 per cent, Plant Protection 3.83 per cent. all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket.

Cost 'B₁' contributes to 60.13 per cent, Cost B₂ contribute 88.69 per cent. The share of family labour was 3.21 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by Medium farmers was 22.07 quintal with gross return of Rs. 108242.34. In case of medium size group the per quintal cost of production was Rs 2955.24

1.3 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for large farmers

It is revealed that from the table 1.3.1 that, the per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean at cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" was Rs. 28836.41, cost "B₁" was Rs.31253.36 whereas cost "B₂" was Rs. 43910.96 and cost

"C₁" was Rs. 32353.29 Cost "C₂" was Rs. 45010.88 whereas cost "C₃" was Rs. 49511.97 The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" (58.24 per cent). In cost "A₁" share of Seed was 13.47 per cent, hired human labour 13.39 per cent, Fertilizer 6.22 per cent, machine hours 2.49 per cent, bullock labour 2.15 per cent, Plant Protection 5.06 per cent. all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket.

Cost B₁ contributes to 63.12 per cent, Cost B₂ contribute 88.69 per cent. The share of family labour was 2.22 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by large farmers was 19.76 quintal with gross return of Rs. 98488.16 In case of large size group the per Quintal cost of production was Rs 2505.66.

Table 1.3.1 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for Large farmers

(Rs/ha)

Sr.No	Item	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost/Unit of input	Total Cost perha	% to cost C ₃
1	Hired Human labour	Male	Days	14.70	296	4410.57	8.91
		Female	Days	11.10	195	2219.80	4.48
		Total				6630.37	13.39
2	Bullock Labour	Hired		1.22	443	734.69	1.48
		Owned		0.66	239	328.80	0.66
		Total				1063.49	2.15
3	Machine Charges	Hired	Hours	0.98	434	682.54	1.38
		Owned	Hours	0.92	339	551.02	1.11
		Total				1233.56	2.49
4	Seed		Kg	61.85	110	6803.94	13.74
5	Manures		Qtls	3.76	160	601.60	1.22
6	Fertilizers	N	Kg	47.01	13.04	613.00	1.24
		P	Kg	50.08	45.25	2265.99	4.58
		K	Kg	10.03	20	200.51	0.40
		Total				3079.49	6.22
8	Irrigation Charges		Rs			298.87	0.60
9	Incidental Charges					295.01	0.60
10	Plant Protection Charges	Rs	Litre			2504.21	5.06
11	Repairing Charges	Rs				535.83	1.08
12	Working Capital					23768.53	48.01
13	Int. on working Capital @ 6%					713.05	1.44
14	Depreciation	Rs				4179.14	8.44
15	Land Revenue	Rs				403.06	0.79
16	Cost A₁					28836.41	58.24
17	Rental value of leased land					0.00	0.00
18	Cost A₂					28836.41	58.24
19	Fixed capital					24169.48	48.82
20	Int. on Fixed Capital @10%					2416.65	4.88
21	Cost B₁					31253.36	63.12
22	Rental value of land	Rs				12657.60	25.56
23	Cost B₂					43910.96	88.69
24	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	2.27	296	680.27	1.37
		Female	Days	2.10	195	419.65	0.85
		Total				1099.93	2.22
25	Cost C₁					32353.29	65.34
26	Cost C₂					45010.88	90.91
27	Cost C₃					49511.97	100.00
28	Main Produce		Qtls	19.76	4808.7	95014.24	191.90
29	By produce		Qtls	10.72	221	3473.92	7.02
30	Gross Value		Rs			98488.16	198.92
31	Per Qtl Cost of Production					2505.66	5.05

Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for overall farmers

It is revealed that from the table 1.4.1 that, the per hectare cost of cultivation of soybean at cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" was Rs. 36511.22, cost "B₁" was Rs. 38396.90 whereas cost "B₂" was Rs. 54141.54 and cost "C₁" was Rs. 41134.74 Cost "C₂" was Rs. 56879.38 whereas cost "C₃" was Rs. 62567.32. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost "A₁" and cost "A₂" (64.19 per cent). In cost "A₁" share of Seed was 13.58. per cent, hired human labour 13.45 per cent, Fertilizer 14.62

per cent, machine hours 7.26 per cent, bullock labour 45.57 per cent, Plant Protection 4.68 per cent. all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket.

Cost 'B₁' contributes to 67.51 per cent, Cost B₂ contribute 86.53 per cent. The share of family labour was 9.20 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by overall farmers was 20.62 quintal with gross return of Rs. 101485.9 In case of overall size group the per Quintal cost of production was Rs. 3034.30

Table 1.4.1 Per hectare Cost of Cultivation of Soybean for Overall farmers

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha	% to cost C ₃
1	Hired Human labour	Male	Days	16.24	225.28	4872.4	8.57
		Female	Days	13.90	150.18	2779.1	4.89
		Total		30.14	375.46	7651.4	13.45
2	Bullock Labour	Hired		3.25	570	10430.5	18.34
		Owned		0.70	216	18081.9	31.79
		Total		3.95	786	28512.4	45.57
3	Machine Charges	Hired	Hours	2.55	583	1783.7	3.14
		Owned	Hours	0.63	196.6	377.3	0.66
		Total		3.18	779.6	4130.2	7.26
4	Seed		Kg	70.23	110	7725.0	13.58
5	Manures		Qtls	7.35	160	1176.0	2.07
6	Fertilizers	N	Kg	46.63	13.04	608.1	1.07
		P	Kg	49.63	45.25	2248.0	3.95
		K	Kg	9.93	20	198.5	0.35
		Total				8317.4	14.62
8	Irrigation Charges		Rs			445.0	0.78
9	Incidental Charges					436.0	0.77
10	Plant Protection Charges		Rs	Litre		2663.5	4.68
11	Repairing Charges		Rs			478.7	0.84
12	Working Capital					33143.8	58.27
13	Int. on working Capital @ 6 %					994.31	1.75
14	Depreciation		Rs			2168.7	3.18
15	Land Revenue		Rs			267.2	0.47
16	Cost A₁					36511.22	64.19
17	Rental value of leased land					0.00	0.00
18	Cost A₂					36511.22	64.19
19	Fixed capital					18856.72	33.15
20	Int. on Fixed Capital @10%					1885.7	3.32
21	Cost B₁					38396.90	67.51
22	Rental value of land		Rs			15762.9	27.71
23	Cost B₂					54141.54	86.53
24	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	6.45	225.28	1933.7	3.40
		Female	Days	4.02	150.18	804.2	1.41
		Total				5233.2	9.20
25	Cost C₁					41134.74	72.32
26	Cost C₂					56879.38	100.00
27	Cost C₃					62567.32	110.00
28	Main Produce		Qtls	20.62	4807.3	99216.5	174.27
29	By produce			9.48	250	2359.3	4.15
30	Gross Value		Rs			101485.9	178.42
31	Per Qtl Cost of Production					3034.30	4.84

Input-Output relationship of Soybean

Efficiency of investment in the cultivation of soybean is judged by calculating Input-Output ratio. The results are presented in Table 1.5.1

Table 1.5.1: Input-Output relationship in Soybean.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Cost A ₁	2.2	2.9	3.4	2.8

2	Cost A ₂	2.2	2.9	3.4	2.8
3	Cost B ₁	2.1	2.7	3.1	2.6
4	Cost B ₂	1.6	1.9	2.2	1.9
5	Cost C ₁	1.9	2.6	3.0	2.5
6	Cost C ₂	1.4	1.8	2.2	1.8
7	Cost C ₃	1.3	1.6	1.9	1.6

Table 1.5.1 revealed that, the input-output ratio overall level i.e. at Cost “A₁”, “A₂”, “B₁”, “B₂”, “C₁”, “C₂”, “C₃” was 2.8, 2.8, 2.6, 1.9, 2.5, 1.8 and 1.6 respectively. The input-output ratio in Small size group farmers at cost A₂ was 2.2, at Cost B₁ was 2.1, at Cost B₂ was 1.6, at Cost C₁ was 1.9, at Cost C₂ was 1.4, at cost C₃ was 1.3. The input-output ratio in Medium size group farmers at cost A₂ was 2.9, at Cost B₁ was 2.7, at Cost B₂ was 1.9, at Cost C₁ was 2.6, at Cost C₂ was 1.8, at Cost C₃ was 1.6. The input-output ratio in Large size group farmers at cost A₂ was 3.4, at Cost B₁ was 2.6, at Cost B₂ was 1.9, at Cost C₁ was 2.5, at Cost C₂ was 1.8, at cost C₃ was 1.6. The results showed that soybean is more profitable crop to large farmers followed by medium farmers.

2. Technical, economic and allocative efficiency of soybean crop

The results of stochastic frontier production function estimates for soybean crop are shown in Table 2.1

The coefficient of Area (0.18), Hired Labour (0.05), Seed (0.29), fertilizer (0.18) was positive and statistically significant. hence the seed under cultivation increases by five per cent it could increase the production 0.26 per cent respectively. The coefficient of cost Machine hours (-0.10) showed a significant negative effect on the yield on soybean production

Parameters	Coefficient	Standard error
Intercept	0.27828	0.30618
Area (X ₁)	0.18999	0.14975
Hired labour (X ₂)	0.05262	0.05796
Seed (X ₃)	0.299**	0.11429
Machine hrs. (X ₄)	-0.01057	0.03314
Fertilizer (X ₅)	0.18749	0.12810
Sigma-squared	0.07228	
Gamma	0.72842	
Log-likelihood value	183.85711	

Table 2.1 Estimation of technical efficiency by using stochastic frontier Production function.

(***, **, * Indicate significance at 1, 5, and 10 per cent level respectively)

2.2: Economic efficiency of soybean crop

Table 2.2.1: Estimation of economic efficiency by using stochastic frontier profit function.

Parameters	Coefficient	Standard error
Intercept	6.85386	0.00553
Area (X ₁)	2.146***	0.00231
Hired labour (X ₂)	0.270***	0.00113
Seed (X ₃)	-0.164***	0.00295
Machine hrs. (X ₄)	-0.184***	0.00116
Fertilizer (X ₅)	-1.117***	0.00288
Sigma-squared	0.67605	
Gamma	1.00000	
Log-likelihood value	-40.11656	

(***, **, * Indicate significance at 1, 5, and 10 per cent level respectively)

The results of stochastic frontier profit function estimates for soybean crop are shown in Table 2.2.1 The coefficient of Area (2.14), Hired Labour (0.27) was positive and statistically significant increases effect on the profit at one per cent level, it could increase the profit at one per

cent level 2.14, 0.27 per cent respectively. The coefficient of seed (-0.16) and Machine hrs. (-0.18), Fertilizer (-1.11) showed a significant negative effect on the profits.

3. Distribution of samples under different levels of production efficiencies

Table 3.1. Distribution of samples under different levels of production efficiency score on soybean

Efficiency score	Technical efficiency		Economic efficiency		Allocative efficiency	
	Frequency	Percentage to total	Frequency	Percentage to total	Frequency	Percentage to total
<10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10.01-20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
20.01-30	0.00	0.00	3.00	2.50	2.00	71.28
30.01-40	0.00	0.00	16.00	13.33	14.00	64.29
40.01-50	0.00	0.00	10.00	8.33	9.00	57.06
50.01-60	0.00	0.00	17.00	14.17	14.00	45.82

60.01-70	0.00	0.00	16.00	13.33	19.00	35.94
70.01-80	0.00	0.00	42.00	35.00	37.00	25.20
80.01-90	31.00	25.83	12.00	10.00	15.00	0.00
>90	89.00	74.17	2.00	1.67	10.00	7.93
Total	120	100	120	100	120	100
Mean TE(%)	95.26		62.72		65.92	
Min TE (%)	82.21		23.99		27.28	
Max TE (%)	99.96		91.15		100.39	

The technical and allocative efficiency scores of soybean growers were calculated and are shown in Table 3.1 According to the soybean producers frequency of technical efficiency score, 31 growers have efficiency between 80.01 and 90 and 89 have efficiency greater than 90. soybean growers had an allocative efficiency score of less than Thirty seven, according to the frequency analysis. Two growers are efficient between 20.01 and 30; Fourteen are efficient between 30 and 40; nine are efficient between 40 and 50; Fourteen are efficient between 50 and 60; Nineteen are efficient between 60.01 and 70; Thirty seven are efficient between 70.01 and 80; Fifteen are efficient between 80.01 and 90; and ten are more efficient than 90. The mean level of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency has been estimated as 95.26 per cent, 62.72 per cent, and 65.92 per cent in soybean cultivation. The result indicates the potential to further improve allocative efficiency by using inputs more efficiently.

Conclusions:

The result revealed that cost of cultivation of soybean was highest in small farmer followed by medium and large farmer. During the survey, it was noted that farmers cultivate soybean under rainfed conditions, with some employing irrigation methods. Uneven rainfall distribution led to water stress in soybean crops during critical growth stages, resulting in decreased yields. To maintain soybean production levels, growers should consider implementing irrigation when necessary.

The mean level of technical efficiency, economic efficiency and allocative efficiency has been estimated as 95.26 per cent, 62.72 per cent, 65.92 per cent in soybean cultivation. The results indicate the potential for improving allocative efficiency further by utilizing inputs more efficiently.

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